

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Long parameter list\]](#) smell? *

In a functional language like Elixir, functions tend to be pure and therefore do not access or manipulate values outside their scopes. Since the input values of these functions are just their parameters, it is natural to expect that functions with a long list of parameters be created to keep them pure. However, when this list has more than three or four parameters, the function's interface becomes confusing and prone to errors during use. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): If a function parameter for some reason is never used, it can be removed using this refactoring.
 - [\[Reorder parameter\]](#): When a function has a long list of parameters that reduces its readability, we can at least reorder the list into a more logical sequence to improve clarity.
1. [\[Grouping parameters in tuple\]](#): If a function has sequential and related parameters in its list, these parameters can be grouped into a *tuple*, thus reducing the length of the list.
 2. [\[From tuple to struct\]](#): A *tuple* used to group parameters can eventually be replaced by a *struct* using this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the ["Use instead of import"] smell? *

This smell occurs when a module relies on "use" to declare dependencies even though an "import" would be sufficient. Typically, "use" implies tighter coupling with the target module. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. **Introduce import**: When a "use" directive is unnecessarily used to establish a dependency between two modules, it can lead to unwanted propagation of internal dependencies from module A to module B. To remove this smell, we can initially replace a "use" directive with an "import" or "alias" directive. For this, we can first use this refactoring, which will create a more superficial dependency in module B with module A.
2. **Remove dead code**: After adding the "import" directive, we should remove the "use" directive using this refactoring.

 - **Alias expansion**: Optionally, if the directive used to replace "use" is an "alias" and it is in the multi-alias format (e.g., `alias Foo.Bar {Baz, Boom}`), we can use this refactoring, thus providing an improvement in code readability and traceability.
 - **Remove import attributes**: Optionally, if after replacing "use" with "import" we identify that a module is excessively importing other modules to the point of impairing readability—making it difficult to identify the origin of the functions it calls—we can perform this refactoring to some unnecessary imports. After that, we will then call the functions from the removed "imports" by their fully-qualified names.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [Speculative assumptions] smell? *

This smell occurs when code makes assumptions that were not planned for, resulting in incorrect return values in situations where a crash would be more appropriate. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- **Introduce pattern matching over a parameter**: This smell arises when developers write defensive or imprecise code, which can return incorrect values that were not planned for. To remove it, we can use this refactoring to force a function to crash instead of returning an invalid value when something unexpected happens.
- **Pipeline using "with"**: If this smell occurs within nested conditional statements, we can use this refactoring to remove them. This operation relies on pattern matching to prevent the continuation of tasks that depend on specific data formats.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Switch Statements\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when the same sequence of conditional statements—whether implemented with if/else, case, cond, or with—appears duplicated throughout the code. As a result, any new check added to these conditionals requires changes in multiple parts of the system. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Replace conditional with polymorphism via Protocols\]](#): Suppose the same sequence of conditional statements appears duplicated in the code. In that case, we may be forced to make changes in multiple parts of the code whenever a new check needs to be added to these duplicated sequences of conditional statements. This refactoring introduces polymorphism to data structures, thus improving the code's extensibility to handle flow controls based on data types.
 2. [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): The inverse operation of this present refactoring can be used to complement the previous refactoring operation, combining polymorphism with guard clauses in the implementation of the functions defined in the created *Protocol*.
- [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): If a switch/conditional of a function is based on a set of numbers or strings that form a list of allowable values for some parameter (i.e., "type code"), we can use this refactoring to replace the conditional with a multi-clause function.
 - [\[Introduce overloading\]](#): We can overload a function, transforming it into a multi-clause function, to eliminate a conditional.
1. [\[Extract function\]](#): Often the duplicated switch/conditional statement switches on a "type code". To isolate a switch/conditional in a *type code host*, start by extracting one of the duplicated switch/conditional statements into a new function.
 2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): Second, the extracted function should be moved to the right module.
 3. [\[Generalise a function definition\]](#): After the previous composite refactoring, the moved function should be transformed into a higher-order function. One of the parameters of this generalized function will receive a function as an argument, responsible for defining the strategy of the internal conditional check.
 4. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): Finally, all points in the code with duplicated switch/conditional statements can use this refactoring to replace the duplicated code with calls to the previously defined higher-order function.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Working with invalid data\]](#) smell? *

This code smell refers to a function that does not validate its parameters' types and therefore can produce internal non-predicted behavior. When an error is raised inside a function due to an invalid parameter value, this can confuse the developers and make it harder to locate and fix the error. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): When a library function does not validate the types of its parameters at its signature, we can at least use this refactoring to document these data. This will help the clients of this function (i.e., third-party code) to protect themselves from potential errors caused by invalid data.
 2. [\[Add type declarations and contracts\]](#): If recurring data structures are found when documenting functions of a library, these structures can be named using the present refactoring, thus creating new reusable data types and increasing the system's readability.
- [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): Optionally, if a client validates the data passed to a library function call using traditional conditional statements, we can use this refactoring to make the client function more idiomatic while still addressing the smell.
 - [\[Struct guard to matching\]](#): Optionally, if a guard clause involving the functions *is_struct/1* or *is_struct/2* is used to avoid working with invalid data, we can use this refactoring to simplify the code used to remove this code smell.
 - [\[Simplifying guard sequences\]](#): Optionally, if a guard clause with redundancies is used to avoid working with invalid data, we can use the present refactoring to also simplify the code used to remove this code smell.
 - [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): Optionally, we can replace guard clauses used in a multi-clause client function to handle invalid data with traditional conditional statements. By doing so, we can use this refactoring to consolidate all data type validations into a single-clause function.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Alternative return types\]](#) smell? *

This code smell refers to functions that receive options (e.g., *keyword list*) parameters that drastically change its return type. Because options are optional and sometimes set dynamically, if they change the return type it may be hard to understand what the function actually returns. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): When a function receives a *Keyword list* as a parameter, which can drastically change its return type depending on its contents, we should initially use this refactoring to create a copy of the original function for each different return type.
2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): After creating the copies, we should rename each one according to its respective return type. Additionally, the bodies of the copies should be modified to fit the specific return types.
3. [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): At this point in the refactoring process, since the *Keyword list* parameter is no longer necessary in any of the renamed copies of the original function, we can use this operation to remove the unnecessary parameter.
4. [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): Finally, we can use this operation on each of the functions involved in this composite refactoring to document their interfaces.
5. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): This refactoring can be used on the copies of the functions created previously in this sequence of transformations to clean up their bodies, removing unused code.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Large messages\]](#) smell? *

When processes exchange messages, their contents are copied between them. For this reason, if a huge structure is sent as a message from one process to another, the sender can become blocked, compromising performance. If these large message exchanges occur frequently, the prolonged and frequent blocking of processes can cause a system to behave anomalously. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Defining a subset of a Map\]](#): If we are originally sending a complete *Map* from one process to another, but actually only need to send a few fields from this *Map*, we can use this refactoring to help reduce the size of the message sent.
- [\[Extract expressions\]](#): When we use *spawn/1* to perform message passing between processes, we can pass an anonymous function as a parameter to *spawn/1* that accesses a *Map* field in its body. This will still copy over all of the *Map*, because the *Map* variable is being captured inside the spawned function. The function then extracts the field, but only after the whole *Map* has been copied over. Suppose we only need to send one field of a *Map* between processes. In that case, we can reduce the size of this message by using this refactoring to store only the necessary value of the *Map* field in a temporary variable. This variable is then used in the spawned function.
- [\[Add a tag to messages\]](#): Optionally, when we are removing this code smell, we may have the opportunity to adapt the processes that communicate with each other by adding tags that identify groups of messages exchanged between them.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

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Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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